

METHODS OF IMPROVING READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS ACCORDING TO PISA INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM

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Abstract. PISA assessment program is an international assessment program that serves to assess literacy in subjects, and is aimed at applying acquired knowledge and skills in life situations, making rational decisions, independent thinking, and forming a worldview. Also, the article reveals the methodology of organizing lessons that serve to form students' reading comprehension and speaking skills based on the current educational content. The mentioned new methods will be useful for students to be able to work with the text, to be able to read it and apply what they understand in practice.

Keywords: PISA 2022 results, skills, thinking, experience, innovation, potential, assessment, competence, program, design, research, critical thinking, ability to analyze text.

The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev PD-5712 dated April 29, 2019 "On approving the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" states that by 2030, "PISA" of the Republic of Uzbekistan will be internationally recognized. It is set to become one of the first 30 advanced countries in the world according to the rating of the student evaluation program.[1] Ensuring the implementation of these decisions imposes on teachers the task of developing new lessons and using new methods in these developments. Considering these processes, we believe the development of methodical recommendations to be the main goal.

PISA 2022 results for Uzbekistan showed significant progress in various fields of education. For the first time, the country participated in the assessment, focusing on reading, math and science. Overall, the results highlighted an improvement in student performance compared to previous benchmarks.

Education reforms and investments in educational quality in Uzbekistan have contributed to this success, reflecting a desire to improve educational outcomes.

Uzbekistan's PISA 2022 results show significant gains in literacy skills among 15-year-old students. This is the first time Uzbekistan has participated in the PISA assessment, and the results highlight strengths in reading comprehension and areas for improvement.

Uzbekistan's participation in the PISA 2022 education assessment showed several important results:

Main attractions:

Overall Improvement: The scores showed a positive trend in students' reading skills compared to previous educational assessments in the country.

Engaging with Texts: Many students demonstrated an ability to understand and interpret a variety of texts, indicating a growing interest in reading.

Weak points:

Critical Thinking: Students struggled with higher order reading skills such as analyzing and evaluating texts. Teachers should focus on developing these critical thinking skills.

Understanding Context: There was a significant gap in students' ability to relate texts to real-world contexts. Including more relevant material related to students' lives can enhance understanding.

Different Text Types: Many students had difficulty with non-fiction and informational texts. Teachers can benefit from diversifying their reading materials to include a wider range of genres.

The following recommendations may be useful for teachers:

Emphasis on critical analysis: encouraging students to ask questions and engage critically with texts.

Use of Diverse Materials: Incorporate a mix of fiction, nonfiction, and diverse media to develop well-rounded reading skills.

Contextual Learning: Integrating real-life events and discussions around reading material to enhance contextual understanding.

Focusing on these areas will help strengthen students' overall reading skills and help prepare them for future assessments.

Emphasizing critical analysis, the following techniques encourage students to ask questions and think critically about texts. We will consider them one by one.

1. Technique of asking questions

Open-ended questions: Encourage discussion with questions that require more than yes/no answers. For example, "What are the author's main arguments and how effectively are they supported?" (Paul, R., & Elder, L. 2014)

Socratic Method: Using a dialogue format that encourages deeper thinking, where students explore complex ideas through guided inquiry.

2. Text analysis

Literary Elements: Teach students to identify and analyze literary elements in texts such as theme, character development, and tone.

Comparative Analysis: Teaches students to compare different texts or authors' points of view, developing analytical thinking. (Foster, T. 2014)

3. Discussion and debates

Class debates: Organize debates on controversial topics from the readings, encouraging students to defend their points of view with evidence. (Johnson, D.W., & Johnson, R.T. 2009)

Small Group Debates: Facilitate small group discussions where students can express their opinions and critique each other's ideas.

4. Writing assignments

Analytical Essays: Assign essays that require students to analyze the argument, structure, and effectiveness of a text. (Graff, G., & Birkenstein, C. 2010)

Reflection Papers: Encourage students to reflect on their learning experiences and express their comments and criticisms.

5. Use of multimedia tools

Films and Documentaries: Analysis of film adaptations to discuss the interpretation and perspective of literary works or related documentaries. (Bordwell, D., & Thompson, K. 2010)

Podcasts and Articles: Include various media formats and have students critically analyze them.

6. Modeling critical thinking

Thinking Aloud: Demonstrate your critical thinking process in analyzing a text, explaining your reasoning, and questioning your conclusions. (Duke, N. K., & Pearson, P. D. 2002).

Graphic organizers: Use tools such as Venn diagrams or T-charts to visually organize comparisons and analyses.

7. Real world connections

Current Affairs: Relating texts to current events or social issues, encouraging students to analyze and discuss their significance. (Habermas, J. 1991)

Guest speakers: Invite authors, journalists or experts to discuss how they approach critical analysis in their fields.

8. Encourage a growth mindset

Emphasize effort: Reinforce the idea that critical analysis is a skill that develops over time and encourages persistence and curiosity. (Dweck, C. S. 2006)

By incorporating these strategies, teachers can create an environment that fosters critical analysis and increases students' ability to engage deeply with texts.

The question arises as to what to do in order to successfully participate in international research such as PISA. To show good results, it is necessary to have at least 2 goals: the first is to prepare teachers and the materials they work with. It is not for nothing that international studies say that the quality of education in schools depends on the professional level of teachers. Therefore, it is necessary to create conditions for investment, financing and methodical support in the system of teacher training. In order to improve the results of international studies, it is necessary to change the teaching methodology and priority principles in the purposeful training of teachers and in the educational process. For this, we need to train teachers, implement a more active system of developmental education, and provide teachers with materials that they can use more successfully in the educational process.

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